

Studies on Solutions of High Dielectric Constant: Part X. Solute solvent interaction in formamide from the solubility data¹

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The enthalpies of solution, in the saturated solution of some electrolytes, calculated from the solubility data, appear to be smaller in formamide and become negative in many cases for which these are positive in aqueous solutions. As a result, the enthalpies of solvation are, in general, numerically larger and negative in formamide, indicating a stronger solute-solvent interaction. Further, in formamide the cations appear to be more solvated than the anions which is contrary to the usually accepted views for aqueous solutions.

Enthalpies of solution, $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ and of solvation, $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$, have been widely used to study solute-solvent interaction. Unfortunately, highly sophisticated apparatus is usually required to determine, $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$, at infinite dilution, specially in non-aqueous solvents in which the solubilities of electrolytes are usually low and the solutes are slow to dissolve. An approximate but convenient method is to calculate $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$, in the saturated solution, from the solubility data and this procedure leads to enthalpies from which, usually, reliable information can be obtained about solute-solvent interaction, specially if the solubilities are low, so that the solution is closer to infinite dilution, as is usually the case with solutions of electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents like formamide³. To study solute-solvent interaction in formamide with this technique, in formamide, the solubilities of some common electrolytes were determined at different temperatures⁴ and $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ were obtained there from. These values have been used to study solute-solvent interaction in formamide in the present communication.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is desirable to summarise here, briefly, the results obtained from the solubility measurements in formamide⁴. Firstly, the solubilities of electrolytes, as well as their rates of dissolution, in general, appear to be smaller in formamide than in water. The dielectric constant of formamide is quite large (109.5⁵ at 25°) and so the belief of some workers⁶ that the reason for ready solubility of so many electrolytes in water is its high dielectric constant, appears to be open to doubt. Factors, other than the dielectric constant, appear to be also important in controlling the solubility. Secondly, the temperature coefficients of solubility of electrolytes are also, in general, smaller in this solvent. Approximate

1. Work supported by the CSIR, India.

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3. Cotton and Brooker, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 1595.

4. Gopal and Husain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 272.

5. Leader, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 856.

6. Robinson and Stokes, "Electrolyte solutions", Butterworths Publications London, 1959, p. 51.

$\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ in the saturated solution, were obtained for different electrolytes, using the molar solubilities at 30° and 40°, the actual values being omitted here for want of space. However, $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ were found to be, in general, smaller in formamide than those in water. In many cases, e.g. NaCl, Ba(NO₃)₂ etc., $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ are actually negative in formamide. These smaller and sometimes negative $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ are indicative of stronger solute solvent interaction as will be more explicit from the considerations to follow.

By combining $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ with lattice enthalpy, U_0 , of the salt in question, one gets the enthalpy of solvation, $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ i.e.

$$\Delta H_{\text{solvation}} = \Delta H_{\text{solution}} - U_0 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

Since $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ are, in general, smaller in formamide than those in water, so $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ would be larger and negative in formamide. Unfortunately, $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$, obtained from the solubility data, are for the saturation state and hence not suitable for quantitative calculations. Instead, $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$, at infinite dilution, obtained by Somsen⁸ for some alkali halides in formamide, are given in Table I. The corresponding $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$, at infinite dilution, for aqueous solutions, are also given in Table I for the sake of comparison.

TABLE I

Electrolyte	$\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ (Kcal) in Formamide	$\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ (Kcal) in Water	Electrolyte	$\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ (Kcal) in Formamide	$\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ (Kcal) in Water
LiF	-240.2	-244.0	KBr	-161.2	-156.6
LiCl	-210.6	-210.1	KI	-152.1	-146.2
LiBr	-204.6	-202.9	RbF	-190.8	-191.8
LiI	-195.7	-192.5	RbCl	-162.1	-158.8
NaF	-216.5	-217.8	RbBr	-155.2	-150.7
NaCl	-187.9	-184.9	RbI	-146.3	-140.3
NaBr	-181.0	-176.8	CsF	-180.5	-181.5
NaI	-171.9	-166.3	CsCl	-154.3	-151.1
KF	-196.7	-197.7	CsBr	-147.2	-142.8
KCl	-168.1	-164.8	CsI	-138.1	-132.4

As may be noted from Table I, that, except for fluorides, $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ are larger and negative in formamide, indicating a stronger solute-solvent interaction as already indicated by the $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ data, obtained from the solubility measurements. It may be interesting to record here that a stronger solute-solvent interaction is indicated by smaller $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ and larger, negative $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$, in N-methylformamide^{9,10} which is a solvent of very high dielectric constant (182.4¹⁰ at 25°). The $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ data, for some alkali metal halide in N-methyl formamide, at infinite dilution, have been reported very recently^{11,12} from which $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ values have been obtained from equation (1) and are given in Table II.

7. Cubicciotti, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, **31**, 1646; 1960, **33**, 1579; 1961, **34**, 2189.

8. Somsen, Thesis: Enthalpies of solvation of alkali halides in formamide: 1964, Vrije University of Amsterdam, Table XIV, p. 55.

9. Bass, Nathan and Cole, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 509.

10. Leader and Gormley, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5731.

11. Weeda and Somsen, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1966, **85**, (ii), 159.

12. Held and Criss, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 2611.

TABLE II

 $\Delta H_{\text{solution}}$ and $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ in N-methylformamide

Electrolyte	$\Delta H_{\text{soln.}}$ (Kcals)		Electrolyte	$\Delta H_{\text{soln.}}$ (Kcals)	
	Held	and Criss ¹³		Weeda and Sornsen ¹⁴	$\Delta H_{\text{soln.}}$ (Kcals)
LiCl	-13.1	-214.6	LiI	-21.14	-198.5
NaCl	-1.12	-187.04	NaI	-8.7	-177.77
NaBr	-4.29	-180.9	KF	-2.63	-196.13
NaI	-8.26	-177.77	KCl	0.374	-168.60
KCl	0.308	-168.60	KBr	-0.825	-162.20
CaCl	0.890	-154.89	KI	-3.23	-154.33
			RbI	-1.65	-148.15
			CsI	0.708	-139.60

Tables I and II clearly show that since $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ values are larger and negative in formamide and in N-methylformamide, solute-solvent interaction is stronger in these solvents as compared to that in water. The larger interaction energy of fluorides in water appears to be due to hydrogen bond interaction of F-with protons which are easily available in aqueous solutions.

Although $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}$ can be calculated directly from Born-Bjerrum equation¹⁵,

$$\text{namely: } \Delta H_{\text{solvation}} = - \frac{N(ze)^2}{2r} \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{\epsilon} - \frac{T}{\epsilon} \left(\frac{d \ln \epsilon}{dt} \right)_p \right\} \quad \text{the ion-}$$

sphere-in-dielectric-continuum model of the authors is far from realistic, specially when the solvent molecule has a large dipole. A more practical approach is to consider ion-dipole interaction. The ion-dipole interaction energy is given by:

$$\Delta E = - e\mu/r^2 \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

y being the electronic charge, μ the dipole moment and r the distance between the centres of the ion and the dipole. Although the structure of the molecule of formamide has been worked out¹⁶, the geometry and layout of the dipole is likely to be influenced in presence of a highly charged ion in its neighbourhood. However, a simple approximate picture may be used for qualitative calculation. It may be assumed that in the formamide molecule, the negative end of the dipole is situated on the oxygen atom of the $>CO$ group and the positive end on the nitrogen atom, shielded by two hydrogen atoms of the $-NH_2$ group. From this simple picture it is easy to see that the value of r , in (2), will be smaller for a cation which attaches itself to the oxygen atom, as compared to that for an anion of the same radius which is attracted towards the nitrogen atom. So from equation (2), the ion-dipole interaction energy for a cation would be larger than that for an anion¹⁶ of the same radius. Also since the dipole moment of formamide is 3.7 D¹⁴ and that for water is 1.8 D, it is reasonable to expect, in general, a stronger ion-solvent interaction (i.e. net solute-solvent interaction) in formamide as compared to that in water.

13. *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1927, 127, 358.

14. Kurland and Wilson, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, 27, 585.

15. Parker, *Quart. Revs.*, 1962, 16, 163.

16. Compare the opposite situation in water (see Rice, 'Electronic Structure and Chemical Binding', McGraw Hill Book Company, Inc., New York, 1940, p. 403.

A stronger cation-solvent interaction in formamide is also supported by studies on transport numbers and mobilities of ions^{17,18}. For the sake of comparison, the cation and anion of the electrolyte should be of equal radii as in KF. Unfortunately, the transport number of either K⁺ ion or of F⁻ of KF, dissolved in formamide, have never been determined. Alternatively, from the knowledge of the experimental transport number of K⁺ ion of KCl in formamide^{17,18} and from the appropriate electrolytic conductance data¹⁹ in this solvent, the mobilities of K⁺ and F⁻ ions in formamide can be estimated to be 12.50 and 15.82 respectively. These values themselves or the transport number (t°), derived therefrom as $t_{+}^{\circ}=0.44$ and $t_{-}^{\circ}=0.56$ at 25°, show clearly that the moving ionic unit of F⁻ in formamide is smaller in size as compared to that for K⁺ ion. Since both bare ions, K⁺ and F⁻, have very nearly the same radius, the difference in the effective sizes in solution must have occurred due to a stronger cation-solvent interaction. As is well known, opposite is the case in aqueous solutions in which the mobility of K⁺ ion is larger than that for the fluoride ion for the reasons discussed by Rice¹⁸. It appears that a relatively weaker cation-solvent interaction in formamide, suggested by Somsen (see ref. 8, p.168), is due to the arbitrary division of the electrolytic enthalpies of solvation by him which is the well-known weakness of the method.

A stronger ion-dipole interaction in formamide indicates a smaller net entropy change on solution as compared to aqueous solutions because there is a net smaller disorder when an electrolyte is dissolved in formamide. In other words, a smaller number of solute molecules (or ions) are able to tie down and immobilize a larger number of solvent molecules which are no longer available for interaction with the solute particles, to enable them to go into solution. So the smaller solubility of electrolytes in formamide appears to be mainly due to the stronger ion solvent interaction in this solvent as compared to that in water.²⁰

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17. Gopal and Bhatnagar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 3892.

18. Nofley and Spiro, *Ibid.*, 1966, 70, 1502.

19. M. M. Husain, Doctorate Thesis: Lucknow University, 1965, p. 75.

20. See ref. 16, p. 405-406.